

1 **Endogenous restriction of CNS malignancy in humans.**

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7 We present evidence here demonstrating the existence of an endogenous anti-tumor program that
8 functions to restrict the growth and spread of CNS malignancy in humans. We identify here genes of the
9 NdrG family as central Myc antagonists in the CNS that possessed restriction factor-like properties in
10 limitation of growth factor and oncogenic factor signaling driven by Myc family in the CNS whose basis
11 was aberrant cycling activity (derestricted proliferation) through a mechanism involving Myc and the N-Myc
12 and Stat interactor, NMI. In humans, Mki67 and PCNA indicate actively or passively the presence of
13 proliferative activity. We identify here a third marker of proliferation, Pea15, that is a CNS-specific marker
14 of proliferation, supporting a specific, active anti-proliferative growth control function in the CNS. Separate
15 from CNS-specific, cell-intrinsic control of the cell cycle involving both an active antagonist function by the
16 NdrG family and an apparently cell-intrinsic anti-proliferative signaling function of Pea15, we observed
17 organization and function of a cell-extrinsic immunologic pathways functioning in endogenous restriction of
18 CNS malignancy. We recently described discovery of the CNS immunologic privilege receptor(s) Ifi2711/12
19 that likely conferred protection against host-derived immune-surveillance in tissues in sensitive organ
20 systems. We demonstrate together that a second, independently functioning immunologic system that
21 controls balance between immune control of proliferative activity in regenerative contexts, or its co-opting
22 by the tumor, and control of oncogenic and microbial activity operating through a collection of cell surface
23 receptor mediated joint innate and adaptive anti-tumor surveillance in the CNS. The evolutionary cost of
24 cross-species CNS invasion in Homo sapiens resulted in adaptive generation of a organized program by
25 which the cells and tissues of the CNS actively restrict malignancy within the CNS.

26 Citations

- 27 1. Ifi27L1/L2 functions in immunologic privilege in the CNS. Mamoor, S. 2025.
- 28